

SHORT NOTES

VOLUMETRIC ESTIMATION OF SILVER

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In the present communication a simple modified volumetric method for the estimation of silver with the aid of common reagents has been suggested. The process consists in precipitation of silver with potassium iodide in presence of hydrogen peroxide and starch solution. The excess of potassium iodide reacts with hydrogen peroxide to liberate iodine, when the last trace of silver has been precipitated. The liberated iodine produces the characteristic blue colour with starch solution. It will be apparent from the experimental results that changes in the concentration, either of the standard solution or of the silver salt, have no influence on the progress of titration. No interference due to the presence of copper in small quantity, zinc, lead, dilute nitric acid, dilute sulphuric acid and oxalic has been observed yet.

Procedure.—The silver salt solution is acidified with 10-20 c.c. of 1:5 H₂SO₄, and to this 5 to 10 c.c. of H₂O₂ (20 vol.) and 2 c.c. of 1% starch solution are added. The solution is then titrated with the standard potassium iodide solution. The end-point is indicated by the blue colour of starch-iodine complex.

The experimental results of a few analyses, according to the present method, are shown in Table I. It also includes the results obtained by the adoption of Volhard's method. It will be evident from the table that results are quite comparable.

TABLE I

Estimation of silver.

0.01N—KI		Ag found by the present method.				0.1N—KI	
		0.0085N—KI					
4.14 mg.	(4.18)mg.	108.4 mg.	(108.4)mg.	107.9 mg.	(107.9)mg.		
5.01	(5.05)	54.2	(54.6)	54.0	(54.5)		
4.50	(4.48)	216.8	(216.8)	215.8	(216.2)		

Figures in parentheses were obtained by Volhard's method.

Further work aiming at studying the influence of interfering substances listed by Hillebrand and Lundell (App. Inorganic Analysis, Rev. Ed., 1953, p. 208) are in progress. It is also proposed to study the suitability of the process in place of assay procedures.

OLEANOLIC ACID FROM *ACHYRANTHES ASPERA* LINN.

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The Indian shrub *Achyranthes aspera* Linn. (Sanskrit: Apamarga) of N. O. Amarantaceae has found use in the Ayurvedic system of medicine against various diseases. The juice of the plant has diuretic and antispasmodic properties. The seeds of the plant were first investigated by Gopalachari and Dhar (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, 11B, 209) who isolated a sapogenin, $C_{29}H_{46}O$, m.p. $305-6^{\circ}$, and a hydrocarbon, m.p. $64-65^{\circ}$. The authors did not suggest anything about the structure of the sapogenin except the observation that it formed a monoacetate, m.p. $298-300^{\circ}$ and gave colour reactions of steroids. More recently Basu *et al.* (*J. Proc. Inst. Chem., India*, 1957, 29, 55, 73, 161) reported the isolation of a nitrogenous compound, $C_6H_{11}O_2N$, H_2O , m.p. $292-3^{\circ}$, from the aqueous extract of the entire plant and they named this compound 'achyranthine'. These workers, however, failed to detect the presence of any glycoside in the plant.

We were interested in the study of the glycosidic fraction of the roots of the shrub. In this communication isolation of oleanolic acid from the glycosidic fraction of the roots is described. The defatted alcoholic extract of the dried roots of the plant was hydrolysed with alcoholic dilute hydrochloric acid and the aglycone fraction was purified by extraction with ether, conversion into the water-insoluble potassium salt and again extraction with ether after acidification. The acid, thus obtained, was converted into the acetate, which was found to be identical with oleanolic acid acetate.

Besides oleanolic acid, no appreciable amounts of any other aglycone could be detected.

Isolation of Oleanolic Acid.—Dried and powdered roots of *Achyranthes aspera* Linn. (670 g.) were extracted for 30 hours in a Soxhlet apparatus with 95% ethyl alcohol. The extract was concentrated to a thick syrup and shaken with 200 c.c. of petroleum ether (b. p. $60-80^{\circ}$). The petroleum ether layer was decanted and the residual glycosidic syrup was further washed thrice with similar 200 c.c. portions of petroleum ether. The dark brown glycosidic residue was dissolved in 100 c.c. of 99% ethyl alcohol and 50 c.c. of water and the solution was refluxed for 4 hours after the addition of 75 c.c. of HCl (conc.). The mixture was cooled, diluted with water and filtered. The filtrate was rejected; the solid residue was washed with water till neutral and then air-dried. The solid was then extracted with ether in a Soxhlet apparatus for 4 hours. The ethereal solution was shaken with 50 c.c. portions of 3% aqueous potassium hydroxide solution and the precipitated potassium salt was filtered off. The ether solution was washed with cold water and evaporated when a very small amount of a tarry neutral product was obtained, which did not yield any crystalline material even after chromatography over alumina.

The aqueous mother-liquor, after the filtration of the solid potassium salt, was acidified with HCl (cold and dilute), when a small amount of a gummy material was precipitated. This gummy acidic material also did not yield any crystalline compound.

Finally, the solid potassium salt was suspended in cold water, acidified with HCl (cold and dilute) and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated, when 0.8 g. of a faintly yellow solid, m.p. $279-98^{\circ}$, was obtained. On repeated crystallisation from methanol and then from acetone, the acid melted at $302-304^{\circ}$, $[\alpha]_D + 79^{\circ}$. These constants agree well with those of oleanolic acid reported by Djerassi and Lippman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 5780).

The acetate of the above acid was prepared in the usual manner by treatment with acetic anhydride and pyridine. The acetate after several crystallisations from methanol and then from acetone, melted at $261-64^{\circ}$, $[\alpha]_D + 77^{\circ}$ (reported m.p. $262-65^{\circ}$, $[\alpha]_D + 77.6^{\circ}$, *loc. cit.*). The acetate did not depress the m.p. of an authentic specimen of oleanolic acid acetate and the infra-red spectrum of our acetate was identical with that of the authentic specimen. (Found: C, 77.40; H, 10.10. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{50}O_4$: C, 77.06; H, 10.11%).

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